

Formation Constants of 5-Nitrosalicylate Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

P. V. KHADIKAR¹, R. L. AMERIA¹ and W. V. BHAGWAT

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain (M.P.)

Manuscript received 30 January 1973; accepted 26 May 1973

Potentiometric study showed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes between copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and 5-nitrosalicylic acid (5NSA). The formation constants of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes have been determined by employing Bjerrum's method. The order of stability is found to be Cu > Ni > Co, which is in accordance with Irving-William rule.

In the previous communications¹⁻⁵ stability constants of Tl^+ , In^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , U^{6+} , Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} chelates of 5NSA were reported. The present investigation deals with the formation of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Co^{2+} chelates with 5NSA.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of either B.D.H. Analar or of equivalent purity.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salts were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity in double-distilled water. pH of the solutions were measured using 'Polymetron CL-41' pH-meter. Other details were the same as described earlier¹⁻⁵.

Results and Discussion

Bjerrum's pH-titration technique⁶ was adopted for obtaining the stepwise stability constants of the complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 5NSA. Since the reagent was insoluble in water, 75% (v/v) aqueous dioxan was used. 0.1M sodium perchlorate was used to maintain constant ionic strength and reaction solutions were all thermostated at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$.

In calculating the values of \bar{n} and $[A^{2-}]$, the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. In this way a series of values of \bar{n} and $[A^{2-}]$, corresponding to different values of pH were obtained in each case and are recorded in Tables 1 to 3.

Formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pA^{2-} , (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. 5-Nitrosalicylates formation curves.

TABLE 1. COPPER(II) 5-NITROSALICYLATE

pH	\bar{n}	Total vol.	$[H^+]^2$	$[H_2A]$	$[A^{2-}]$	pA^{2-}
2.50	0.12	51.0 ml	1.00×10^{-5}	7.84×10^{-3}	2.83×10^{-9}	8.5482
2.60	0.18	52.3	6.31×10^{-6}	7.65	4.38	8.3585
2.70	0.22	54.0	3.98	7.41	6.72	8.1726
2.80	0.32	55.7	2.51	7.18	1.033×10^{-8}	7.9859
2.90	0.42	57.0	1.58	7.02	1.60	7.7959
3.00	0.55	58.0	1.00	6.90	2.49	7.6138
3.10	0.70	59.0	6.31×10^{-7}	6.78	3.88	7.4112
3.20	1.06	59.8	3.16	6.69	6.66	7.1805
3.30	1.52	60.0	2.51	6.66	9.57	7.0191
3.40	1.76	60.5	1.58	6.61	1.50×10^{-7}	6.8825
3.50	1.84	61.0	1.00	6.55	2.36	6.6271
3.75	2.00	62.3	3.16×10^{-8}	6.43	6.34	6.1979

1. Department of Chemistry, Madhav Science College, Ujjain, (M.P.).

The values for $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ of copper, nickel and cobalt 5-nitrosalicylates were directly read from their formation curves.

TABLE 2. NICKEL(II) 5-NITROSALICYLATE

pH	\bar{n}	Total vol.	$[H^+]^2$	$[H_2A]$	$[A^{2-}]$	pA^{2-}
2.85	0.08	55.8 ml	1.99×10^{-6}	7.17×10^{-3}	1.30×10^{-8}	7.8861
2.95	0.12	57.0	1.26	7.02	2.03	7.6925
3.10	0.16	58.5	6.31×10^{-7}	6.81	3.91	7.4089
3.40	0.17	60.4	1.58	6.62	1.43×10^{-7}	6.8462
3.50	0.20	60.7	1.00	6.58	2.38	6.6244
3.60	0.26	60.9	6.31×10^{-8}	6.57	3.76	6.4246
3.70	0.36	61.0	3.98	6.55	5.94	6.2262
3.80	0.56	61.2	2.51	6.53	9.39	6.0273
3.90	1.36	61.3	1.58	6.52	1.49×10^{-6}	5.8283
4.00	1.80	61.4	1.00	6.51	2.35	5.6289

TABLE 3. COBALT(II) 5-NITROSALICYLATE

pH	\bar{n}	Total vol.	$[H^+]^2$	$[H_2A]$	$[A^{2-}]$	pA^{2-}
3.20	0.10	59.2 ml	3.98×10^{-7}	6.75×10^{-3}	6.12×10^{-8}	7.2132
3.40	0.14	60.3	1.58	6.63	1.51×10^{-7}	6.8210
3.60	0.18	60.9	6.31×10^{-8}	6.56	3.76	6.4248
3.80	0.26	61.3	2.51	6.52	9.38	6.0278
3.90	0.32	61.4	1.58	6.51	1.48×10^{-6}	5.8291
4.00	0.38	61.5	1.00	6.50	2.35	5.6302
4.10	0.48	61.6	6.31×10^{-9}	6.49	3.71	5.4306
4.30	1.52	61.7	2.51	6.48	9.31	5.0311
4.60	1.96	61.8	6.31×10^{-10}	6.47	3.70×10^{-5}	4.4315
5.30	2.05	61.9	2.51×10^{-11}	6.46	9.29×10^{-4}	4.0230

TABLE 4. STABILITIES OF METAL CHELATES OF 5-NITROSALICYLIC ACID

Metal	At. No.	2nd I.P.	Elec. nety.	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2
Copper	29	20.34	1.75	7.65	7.05	14.70
Nickel	28	18.20	1.75	6.12	5.80	11.92
Cobalt	27	17.30	1.70	5.38	5.04	10.42

Table 5 gives the pH values for metal 5-nitrosalicylates when $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ along with the pH at which the hydrolysis of the metal starts. The value of pH at $\bar{n} = 1.5$ is of interest as it should be lower than the pH at which the hydrolysis of metal commences.

TABLE 5. pH VALUES OF CHELATES AT $\bar{n} = 0.5$ AND $\bar{n} = 1.5$

Metal	pH at $\bar{n} = 0.5$	pH at $\bar{n} = 1.5$	pH at which hydrolysis of metal starts
Copper	3.00	3.80	5.30
Nickel	3.70	4.15	6.90
Cobalt	4.00	4.30	7.00

Table 5 shows that pH at $\bar{n} = 1.5$ is lower than that at which the hydrolysis of the metal starts in all the cases. Hence the hydrolysis of the metal ions is not likely to interfere in the determination of stability constants. Moreover, there was no precipitation during chelation titrations, which clearly rules out the possibility of the hydrolysis of these metal ions in the presence of a large excess of the ligand.

Table 4 indicates that log K_1 , log K_2 and log β_2 values of 5-nitrosalicylates follow the order :

Copper > Nickel > Cobalt

in accordance with Irving-William rule⁷.

A parallelism between log K_n and 2nd I.P. is noted (fig. omitted) in the present case also, as pointed by Irving and William⁷. Except in the case of zinc, this potential indicates the energy required for the removal of a d -electron showing that d -orbitals are involved in the chelation.

Acknowledgement

The authors' thanks are due to the U.G.C. for a research grant.

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